

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE STUDY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

Rakhmatullayeva Muslima Baxtiyorjon kizi
Student of Uzbek state world languages university
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6660613>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022
Accepted: 02nd June 2022
Online: 15th June 2022

KEY WORDS

Key words:
phraseology,
phraseological units,
translation, figurativeness,
equivalents, phrases.

ABSTRACT

This article deals with phraseology as an object of linguistic research and their classifications, as well as some more essential data concerning translation of phraseological units and its obstacles which translator might come across during interpretation.

In recent decades, there has been an active process of systematic study of lexical and phraseological units in various respects - semantically, grammatically, stylistically in English sphere.

A number of works of local scholars have studied the semantics of phraseological units, set specific features of the meaning of phraseological units in relation to units at the lexical and syntactic level.

Phraseology (Greek phrasis - "expression", logos - "teaching") is a branch of linguistics that studies stable combinations in a language.

The tasks of phraseology as a linguistic discipline include a comprehensive study of the phraseological fund of a particular language. Important aspects of the study of this science are: the stability of phraseological units, the consistency of phraseology and the semantic structure of phraseological units, their origin and main functions. A particularly complex branch of

phraseology is the translation of phraseological units, which requires considerable experience in the study of this discipline.

Translating phraseological units into English is a very difficult task. "Due to its semantic richness, figurativeness, conciseness and brightness, phraseology plays a very important role in the language". It gives speech expressiveness and originality. Especially widely phraseological units are used in oral speech, in fiction and political literature. When translating a phraseological unit, the translator needs to convey its meaning and reflect its figurativeness, finding a similar expression in English and not losing sight of the stylistic function of the phraseological unit. In the absence of an identical image in the English language, the translator is forced to resort to the search for an "approximate match".

Phraseological equivalents can be full and partial.

Complete phraseological equivalents are those ready-made English equivalents that coincide with Russian ones in meaning, lexical composition, figurativeness, stylistic coloring and grammatical structure; for example: *почить (почивать) на лаврах* – rest on one's laurels, *соль земли* – the salt of the earth, *играть с огнем* – to play with fire, *час настал (пробил)* – one's hour has struck, *нет дыма без огня* – there is no smoke without fire, *трудолюбивый как пчела* – busy as a bee.

Translation based on partial phraseological equivalents does not at all mean that in this case the meaning and figurativeness of phraseological units are not fully transmitted in translation; By this term, one should mean that in the equivalent offered in English, some discrepancies with Russian are possible. In other words, for a translator “when translating a phraseological unit, it is important, first of all, to convey the image of a phraseological unit, and not its linguistic structure”. Partial phraseological equivalents can be divided into three groups.

The first group includes phraseological units that coincide in meaning, stylistic coloring and are similar in figurativeness, but diverging in lexical composition: *сулить золотые горы* – to promise wonders, to promise the moon, *в гостях хорошо, а дома лучше* – East or West, home is the best, *купить кошку в мешке* – to buy pig in a poke, *первая ласточка* – the first portent (sign), *овчинка выделки не стоит* – the game is not worth the candle, *притча во языцех* – the talk of the town.

Some of these phrases are translated using antonymic translation, i.e. a negative value

is conveyed by the translator using an affirmative construction or, conversely, a positive value is conveyed using a negative construction: *цыплят по осени считают* – don't count your chickens before they are hatched.

The second group includes phraseological units that coincide in meaning, figurativeness, lexical composition and stylistic coloring; but differ in such formal features as the number and order of words, for example: *играть на руку кому-либо* – to play into smb.'s hands (there is a discrepancy in the number); *не все то золото, что блестит* – all is not gold that glitters (discrepancy in word order); *за деревьями не видать леса* – not to see the wood for the trees (discrepancy in word order).

The third group includes phraseological units that coincide in all respects, with the exception of figurativeness. In Russian we speak - *отправиться на боковую*, while the English equivalent would be the usual – to go to bed. There is a phraseology in Russian – *быть как на ладони*, and in English in such cases it is customary to say – to spread before the eyes, to be an open book. In Russian we speak – *старо, как мир*, and in English the same idea is conveyed by phraseology – as old as the hills.

Phraseological units are widely used in literature of all styles. And a competent translator should not allow inaccuracies in the translation of this or that phraseological unit. Without knowledge of phraseology, it is impossible to appreciate the brightness and expressiveness of speech, to understand a joke, a play on words, and sometimes simply the meaning of the entire statement.

. The translation of phraseological expressions from English into other languages causes certain difficulties due to their semantic integrity and complexity. A literal (literal) translation of a phraseological expression distorts the meaning of the statement, an adequate transfer of the meaning of the phraseological unit into the second language is required.

There are the following ways of translating phraseological expressions:

1) equivalent - translation of a phraseological unit from the first language by a phraseological unit of the second language, coinciding with it in meaning and in the structural composition of the components. Absolutely adequate phraseological expressions of two languages are called full (or absolute) equivalents: to pull chest nuts out of the fire for smb. - таскать каштаны из огня для кого-либо; to stew in one's own juice - рус. вариться в собственном соку; wolf in sheep's clothing - рус. волк в овечьей шкуре,

Incomplete (or partial) equivalents are those phraseological expressions that have structural and grammatical or lexical differences, when one component of the phraseological expression of the English language does not coincide with the phraseological expression of the second language, but belongs to the same thematic group: like a squirrel in a cage - рус. как белка в колесе (дословно как белка в клетке); to get out of bed on the wrong side - рус. встать с левой ноги.

2) similar - translation of a phraseological expression from the first language by a phraseological unit of the second language,

adequate in content, but different in structural and component composition. For example, as stiff as a poker (дословно застывший как кочерга); a fly in the ointment (дословно муха в мази) - рус. ложка дёгтя в бочке мёда,

(дословно похож как две горошины) - рус. как две капли воды, one's in a blue moon

(дословно однажды приглубой луне) - рус. когда раз на горесвистнет; to make a mountain out of a mole hill (дословно сделать гору из кротовины) - рус. делать из мухи слона.

3) descriptive - translation of a phraseological expression descriptively or by one equivalent word, or by a group of equivalent words (in the event that the second language does not have a phraseological unit corresponding to the phraseological unit of the first language). For example, a white elephant (дословно белый слон) - рус. обременительное или разорительное имущество; a burden, a gift that you don't know how to get rid of; to knit one's brows (дословно связать, сращивать чьи-либо брови); red tape (дословно красная лента) - волокита, бюрократизм; to fiddle while Rome is burning

(дословно играть на скрипке в то время как да горит Рим) заниматься пустяками перед лицом серьёзной опасности; ships that pass in the night (дословно корабли, которые проплывают мимо вночи) - мимо лётных встречи; a black sheep (дословно чёрная овца) - позор семье.

4) combined transfer - the transfer is carried out by a combination of the above methods. Phraseological expression-analogue and equivalent plus descriptive

translation. This method is used when the phraseological unit of the second language does not fully reveal the meaning of the phraseological expression of the first language. For example, spick and span - рус.сиголочки, элегантный, щегольской; far cry (дословнодалёкийкрик) - рус. какнебоиземля; большаяразница; a mill stone about smb's neck (дословножёрновбремя) вокругчьей-либошеи) - рус. каменьнашее; тяжёлаяответственность; to live on the fat of the land (дословножитьнажирнойземле) - рус.кататьсякаксырвмасле; житьвроскоши, житьприпеваючи.

To conclude, the English language has a fairly diverse and extensive structure. Despite this, it cannot be said for sure that this language is difficult to learn. However, during the initial acquaintance with him, a person has a number of difficulties that he sometimes cannot cope with, unless he studies with a strong and talented teacher, or, alternatively, resorts to the help of a tutor. One of the difficulties in learning English is as it was mentioned above, the topic of prepositions and phraseological units because of having a fairly large number of prepositions, as well as rules for their use in English which is worth to learn more deeply.

References:

1. Stylistics of the English language: a textbook for ints and f-tov foreign . lang. / A. N. Morokhovsky, O. V. Vorobieva, N. I. Likhosherst, Z. V. Timoshenko. Kyiv, 1991
2. Sokolova E.I. English language. Prepositions [Text] / E.I. Sokolov. M.: Livinglanguage, 2016. - 224 p.